

Olena CHUKHNO

PhD in Education, Associate Professor
H. S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University

STAGES OF DEVELOPING VOCABULARY NOTICING SKILLS IN PRE-SERVICE EFL TEACHERS

One of the most natural ways to acquire a language is by “picking it up” through exposure to authentic content, e.g., texts, videos, and audio materials. Yet this process is far from passive. As learners engage with English-language input, they inevitably come across words and structures that are unfamiliar or only half-known, and this is precisely at this moment that real acquisition takes place. A learner might wonder whether they have heard some word before, what it might mean in that context, how different it is from what they already know. These instinctive questions develop linguistic awareness, sharpen the ability to notice new language items, and help learners to gradually transfer new items from passive recognition into long-term memory and, eventually, active production.

However, noticing does not occur automatically. Without explicit guidance, many learners simply read or listen for the gist, bypassing unfamiliar vocabulary. Thus, noticing skills need to be actively and deliberately cultivated.

This becomes particularly important in pre-service teacher education. Future EFL teachers face a dual challenge: they must continue developing their own English proficiency while simultaneously learning to foster language awareness in their future students. This dual role means that developing noticing skills in pre-service teachers cannot follow the same path as it does for ordinary language learners: it must incorporate a professional, pedagogical, dimension.

The role of noticing in second language acquisition has been widely discussed since Schmidt (1990) proposed his influential noticing hypothesis, arguing that conscious attention to linguistic input is a necessary condition for acquisition, i.e. what learners notice in input is what becomes intake in learning. Schmidt further identifies noticing as the point where external factors (input complexity, task design, instruction) and internal ones (motivation, aptitude, prior knowledge) converge to enhance language development (Schmidt, 2010). Cross also highlights the role of instruction, input frequency, perceptual salience, learners’ skill level, and task requirements as key factors affecting noticing (Cross, 2002). Nifli-Sakali emphasizes that noticing is most effective when paired up with communicative tasks, authentic input, and meaningful opportunities for language production (Nifli-Sakali, 2023).

Despite this body of research, the question of how noticing skills should be developed in pre-service teachers, who must grow both as language users and as future educators, has received little systematic attention. Therefore, the aim of the

study is to identify and describe the stages of developing vocabulary noticing skills in pre-service teachers of English, offering a framework that accounts for both their language development and their professional preparation.

We believe that the proposed framework should begin with four stages applicable to all language learners.

The first stage is raising awareness. Before any noticing can occur, learners must understand why it matters, that stopping to examine an unfamiliar word is not an interruption to learning but an integral part of it.

The second stage involves exposure and attention. Engaging with authentic and pedagogically designed input, learners practice identifying unfamiliar or partially familiar vocabulary rather than skipping over it, developing a heightened lexical alertness.

The third stage is noticing the gap, i.e. the analytical process of examining how a new language item differs from what students already know. This may involve morphological analysis, contextual inference, informed guessing, and attention to pronunciation and grammatical features. All these operations turn a moment of uncertainty into genuine linguistic inquiry.

The fourth stage is validation. Learners test their initial hypothesis by consulting a dictionary, asking their teacher, or working collaboratively with peers. This stage does not only confirm accuracy, but also builds learners' confidence in their own analytical process and encourages independent noticing in the future.

For pre-service teachers, the four stages above remain fully relevant. Two additional stages, however, may extend the process into a professional dimension.

At the fifth stage, pre-service teachers reflect on what triggered their own noticing, e.g., whether it was a word stress or intonation in spoken input, a typographical feature (bold text, italics, capitalization), or explicit instruction in the task. By examining the mechanisms behind their own attention, pre-service teachers develop an understanding of how vocabulary salience is created.

The sixth stage moves from reflection to professional action. Drawing on their own experience as 'noticers,' pre-service teachers explore how to create similar moments of noticing for their future students. Graphically, this might mean highlighting, contrasting fonts, or using capital letters in written materials. Orally, it might involve strategic pauses, emphatic stress, or intonation. Explicitly, it might take the form of targeted task instructions, for instance, asking learners to note the adjectives a speaker uses, or to identify words that feel unexpected in a given context. At this stage, pre-service teachers turn from being recipients of noticing-focused instruction into becoming its designers.

In conclusion, we propose a six-stage framework for developing vocabulary noticing skills in pre-service EFL teachers. Based on Schmidt's noticing hypothesis and related second language acquisition research, the framework moves from basic awareness-raising and analytical engagement with unfamiliar vocabulary to designing noticing-focused instruction on one's own.

Future research may deal with empirical validation of the proposed framework. Extending the framework to cover grammatical noticing and phonological noticing also remains a worthwhile direction for future work.

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